

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' DECISION TO ENROLL IN AGRICULTURE COURSES IN DAVAO DEL NORTE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 6

Pages: 827-840

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2195

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13309815

Manuscript Accepted: 07-08-2024

Factors that Influence Senior High School Students' Decision to Enroll in Agriculture Courses in Davao del Norte

Jonathan M. Almanzor,* Chenie Kate Almanzor
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to explore the factors that influence senior high students' decisions to enroll in agriculture courses in college. Specifically, this sought answers to the socioeconomic profile of senior high school students and determined the environmental condition of the senior high school students in terms of external factors (family income and parents' educational attainment) and internal factors (type of school as public or private, and strand taken). A quantitative technique using descriptive causal research design was utilized to attain its objectives. 1645 Senior High School students from the 11 municipalities or cities in Davao del Norte were respondents to the study. Generally, a self-made survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data. The data were tallied and treated with appropriate statistical tools. It was found that the environmental conditions of SHS in terms of family income and parents' educational attainment as external factors were sometimes evident and in terms of the type of school and strand taken, these internal factors were sometimes evident. It was found out that in terms of social learning, this factor was sometimes evident, in terms of cognitive, this factor was oftentimes evident, in terms of affective, this factor was oftentimes evident, in terms of subjective norm, this factor was sometimes evident, and in terms of perceived behavioral control, this factor was oftentimes evident. It was found that there existed a positive significant influence of environmental, cognitive, and subjective norms factors towards SHS's decision to enroll in an agriculture course in college, however, no significant influence existed on social learning, affective and perceived behavioral control factors towards SHS choice to enroll on agriculture course in college. Finally, the researcher recommends that similar studies may be conducted using other theories and methods, to be conducted in different locales and considering the limitations of this study to further validate its results.

Keywords: *socioeconomic profile, environmental conditions, social learning, cognitive, affective, subjective norm*

Introduction

The rate of development needed to address the challenges in the agricultural industry cannot be sustained without an adequate supply of qualified agricultural professionals. As such, concern about the recruitment of students to enroll in agriculture courses has been significant, and much research has been devoted to identifying and addressing the problem (Mallory & Sommer, 2016). However, colleges of agriculture across the world have seen a decline in enrollment during the past decades and the number of graduates seeking careers in agriculture each year has remained less than the number of job positions to be filled despite of the greater efforts made (Baker, 2023).

In California, agricultural programs enrollment showed a significant decrease. As such, a reduction in the number of individuals who sought educational training in agriculture was observed. Such decline in enrollment is due to the past and present agricultural economic crises which caused negative impacts on career decisions concerning agricultural occupations (Bowen, 2016). Moreover, in Oregon, shortage of funds resulting to inadequate facilities and amenities is seen to affect students' decision to enroll in agricultural programs. The school budgetary constraints have caused school administrators to look more closely at the relatively high cost which students have to shoulder. As a result, students opt to enroll on other courses which resulted to a decline enrollment in agricultural courses (Price, 2019). While, in New York, student's decision to enroll in agricultural education programs is affected by intrapersonal factors including interests, attitudes, and value systems, as well as perceptions of course content, pedagogical strategies, and career potential. Also, sociocultural factors, including gender and ethnicity, have been shown to affect student attitudes, beliefs, and enrollment in agricultural courses (Sutphin et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, specifically, in the provinces of Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR) enrollment in agriculture courses has been declining over the years, which have contributed to the dwindling number of agriculture specialists in the sector. This may have contributed to the very low share of agriculture gross value added (GVA) to the total regional output of only 2% while employing about 43% of the region's workforce as of 2017 (NEDA, 2018). Parental education, family income, and peers are seen to have an influence on students' choice to enroll on agricultural programs which may have significant effect on the aforesaid (Rababah, 2016). Also, personal interests, gender, career opportunity and availability of jobs are some of the factors that significantly influence students decision to enroll in agricultural courses (Kaneez & Medha, 2018). Moreover, the psychological support provided by the family members, school friends, teachers, and the community are seen to impact senior high school students' decision to enroll in agriculture courses, which are seen to affect also their behavior towards agriculture courses (Wildman & Torres, 2022), as expounded by Bozgeyikli (2020) that the psychological needs constitutes the fundamentals of individual behaviors. As such, these factors should be given utmost attention and concern, otherwise a declining trend of students enrolling in agricultural programs shall continue.

In Davao Region, agriculture is perceived by students as a difficult job, and low-income generating occupation. Also, they think that farming requires a lot of efforts which caused them to lose their confidence to do this kind of work (Reyes, 2019). Consequently, Nazareno et al. (2021) divulged that family influence, personal influence, financial stability, employment and salary security, and the capability of doing work influence students' decisions to enroll in agriculture. Also, opportunities such as scholarships, and aid from various networks to pursue studies affect students' decisions to enroll in agricultural courses (Wildman & Torres, 2022). In effect, enrollment in agriculture and related courses continues to go down despite the increasing demand for food and other farm products in the locality for the past years (searca.org). As such, there is a necessity to explore on these factors to be able to substantially understand the underlying causes why only few of the senior high school students opt to choose agricultural courses.

Although there has been some early research about the students' rationale for selection of agriculturally related courses (Sutphin et al., 2019) and on global influential factors for choice of agriculture related courses among students (Manyasi, 2021), however, these studies are univariate in nature and may have not totally explored the factors why enrollment on agricultural courses, still shows a decreasing trend. Further, there is limited research that specifically focuses on the factors that influence senior high school students' decisions to enroll in agriculture courses in college especially within the locale of the study. This gap in the literature suggests a need for thorough investigation to understand the factors that are contributing to this decline in enrollment in agriculture courses. As such, understanding these factors can help educators and policymakers develop effective strategies to encourage more students to pursue agricultural courses in college, which can lead to the development of a more sustainable and resilient agricultural sector.

Research Questions

Despite the importance of the agriculture sector in the economy, the number of students who choose to study agriculture in college has been declining. Moreover, considering the relevance of the agriculture sector to demographic trends and growth, evidences reveal that careers in agriculture are not favored by students. Also, there is a dearth of research-based knowledge that could help colleges of agriculture with their recruitment procedures and campaign to increase enrollment and eventually encourage more senior high school students to choose agricultural courses in college by giving in-depth attention to the factors that influence their decisions.

Apparently, this study aimed to fill the aforementioned gaps by exploring on the factors that influence senior high school students' decisions to enroll in agriculture in Davao del Norte. This study shall contribute to the understanding of the factors and how these factors could possibly resolved the problem of the declining enrollment of students on agriculture courses. Also, there is a need for a thorough investigations on these factors so that possible areas of improvement for an effective strategies and plan of actions could be provided aimed at increasing the students' enrollment on agriculture courses.

Lastly, this study aimed to explore the factors that influence senior high students' decisions to enroll in agriculture courses in college. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socioeconomic profile of the senior high school students?
2. What is the environmental condition of the senior high school students in terms of external factors (family income and parents' educational attainment) and internal factors (type of school as public or private, and strand taken).
3. What are the behavioral factors of senior high school students in terms of social learning, cognitive, affective, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control?
4. What are the factors influencing the decision of senior high school students to enroll in agricultural courses?

Literature Review

Factors that Influence Senior High School Students' Decisions to Enroll in Agriculture

As divulged by Reyes (2019), family influence, personal influence, financial stability, employment and salary security, and the capability of doing work affect students' decisions in choosing agricultural courses. Likewise, students' impression on farming, as well as their knowledge and confidence to do farming job play a huge part in their decisions to enroll in agricultural courses in college.

Moreover, socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, and socioeconomic status are among the factors that influence the career track choice of senior high school students. In fact, as revealed by Kim (2021) men and women may differ in their ways of thinking when making a choice; men are more liberal and progressive, while women engage more in hierarchical thinking. Also, age is a significant predictor, as unwrapped by Schein (2018). And as unveiled by Wang and Degol (2018), socioeconomic status, such as the family's monthly income and parents' educational attainment and occupation, motivates students' career choices in agriculture.

On the one hand, in the study of Fizer (2018), academic performance is also one of the factors deemed significant in choosing a career in agriculture. Students who possess the ability to manage heavy academic workloads tend to choose a career path that would lead to a career demanding long years of education. Meanwhile, students who lack sufficient intellectual aptitude may be more suitable for career fields requiring less extensive and challenging academic work.

Further, as unconcealed by Lent (2018), interest is one of the personality factors playing a significant role in career decision-making in agriculture. Individuals who choose a career that matches his/her interests are likely to feel more satisfied and motivated. Likewise, Spokane (2019) disclosed that interests and chosen career are positively related to academic performance, academic persistence,

satisfaction, and ego strength. On the contrary, students who are forced to take a specific career showed low self-esteem and poor performance.

Consequently, parents as students' primary support system, influence their educational aspirations, work ethics and values, and motivation (Alphones, 2016). Also, Udoh and Sanni (2017) have shown that parents' educational attainment influences students' career choices in agriculture. On the contrary, Alphones (2016) mentioned that children whose parents complain about the struggle to support the family with their income are likely to take a career field that could lead to a job with higher earnings.

Furthermore, social influences are environmental factors considered by students before making a career decision in agriculture (Johnson Mortimer 2022). These include the impact of family members, school friends, teachers, and the community. As unveiled by Wildman and Torres (2022), family and friends play a crucial role in influencing an individual in choosing a career in agriculture. Also, Pimpa (2023) undraped that influence of family, peer, and student recruitment provide psychological support to students in the career selection process. Additionally, the family's cultural and social context and the community play a significant role in informing and influencing students about choosing a career in agriculture (Ferry, 2016).

In addition, opportunities such as scholarships, aid from various networks to pursue studies, and family with high financial capability affect how a student decides which career path in agriculture to take. Students with these opportunities have more freedom to choose which path they want, whereas students who do not possess these favorable circumstances have limited options (Cross & Slater, 2017). Apparently, when students aspire for a career path in agriculture, they look for fields that could lead them to employment to provide financial security and career advancement (Wildman & Torres, 2022).

Adding on, Uyar et al. (2021) revealed that high earnings expectations, career expectations, job experience, knowledge and ability, family environment, social status, and education environment are some of the factors affecting the decision of students' career choice in agriculture. Seemingly, as unconcealed by Yazici and Yazici (2020), interest in the subject, guaranteed employment, and expected earnings after graduation are the most influential factors for agriculture courses choice among students.

Likewise, Sutphin et al. (2019) unwrapped that student's decision to enroll in agricultural education programs is affected by intrapersonal factors including interests, attitudes, and value systems, as well as perceptions of course content, pedagogical strategies, and career potential. Sociocultural factors, including gender and ethnicity, have also been shown to affect student attitudes, beliefs, and enrollment in agricultural courses is needed to facilitate recruitment and inform guidance counseling and curriculum development.

On the other note, student misconception of the agricultural industry and agricultural career opportunities may negatively affect recruitment (Krueger & Riesenberg, 2021). Most of the senior high school students are unaware of the range of agricultural careers, rate of agricultural jobs in terms of stability, a secure future, and earning power (Mallory & Sommer, 2016). Correspondingly, limited understanding of vocational agriculture and agricultural employment, and inadequate understanding of agriculture may hinder parents' ability to counsel their children in these areas (Hoskey, 2018).

Moreover, beliefs and attitudes are predictors in choosing a career in agriculture as disclosed by Lam (2022). These intrapersonal factors are potential barriers that influence students not to enroll in agriculture course including attitudes, perceptions, images, motivation, career maturity, and value systems. Personal issues, on the other hand, may also encourage enrollment in agriculture (Rossetti et al., 2020). For instance, Cano and Bankston (2022) found out that students' choice in enrolling in agriculture course is a result of the influence of friends or relatives, or interest in the development of leadership skills and self-confidence. Besides, Marshall et al. (2022) opined that activities, experiences, and youth development opportunities and activities affect student enrollment in agriculture.

Lastly, Manyasi (2021) stressed that situational factors in the teaching and learning process such as academic success which is influenced by factors such as school safety and adaptive grouping, and improvements in school situations such as improved school funding and student discipline affect students' choice to study agriculture.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the quantitative technique using descriptive causal research design to attain its objectives. Quantitative research narrows itself to statistical analyses of collected data via survey questionnaires employing computational approaches (Trefry, 2017).

In this study, quantitative technique was used in explore the factors that influence senior high students' decisions to enroll in agricultural courses in college. Also, it was used to determine the relationship between variables of the study; the independent variables which include environmental, cognitive, and affective factors; the dependent variable which is the senior high school students' decision to enroll in agriculture courses and the moderating variables which include subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

Adding on, descriptive causal research design is also known as explanatory research is conducted in order to identify the extent and nature of cause-and-effect relationships. Causal research can be conducted in order to assess impacts of specific changes on existing norms, various processes etc. Also, causal studies focus on an analysis of a situation or a specific problem to explain the patterns of

relationships between variables.

In this study, a descriptive causal research design was used to find out if environmental, cognitive, and affective factors could significantly influence senior high school students' decision to enroll in agriculture courses in college; and if subjective norms and perceived behavioral control could moderate the relationship between personal, environmental, and behavioral factors and senior high school student's decision to enroll in agriculture courses in college.

Respondents

In choosing the respondents, stratified random sampling was used. However, the sample size from each strata was determined using a Raosoft Calculator considering a 5% margin of error. The researcher made sure that proportional sampling was done by making sure that each municipality/city within the locale of the study was represented.

Further, stratified random sampling involves the division of a population into smaller subgroups known as strata (Hayes, 2022). In this study, the senior high school students was grouped according to municipality or city. This was done to get the proportionate representation of senior high school students from each municipality or city which the researcher believed to affect the results of the study.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents from the 11 municipalities or cities in Davao del Norte which are coded as A, B, C,... and so on. It could be gleaned on the table that there were 1,645 senior high school students who were able to respond to the survey questionnaire.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>City/Municipality</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
A	280
B	216
C	207
D	55
E	105
F	122
G	110
H	203
I	152
J	130
K	65
Total	1645

Moreover, in reference to the sample size, an estimate non-response rate of 30 percent was considered. This rate was taken into account as higher response rates guarantee survey results with greater accuracy (Rea & Parker, 2018). Specifically, a 70 percent response rate is believed to be reasonable in a survey of general population that aims to describe knowledge or behaviors (Gordon, 2018).

Instruments

Quantitative researcher uses varied sources of data to understand the topic or subject that they want to investigate. Surveys and experiments are the common data sources for quantitative research. Moreover, the data collected are typically in the form of numbers, such as response frequencies, means, and standard deviations, and can be analyzed using statistical software (Trefry, 2017).

In this study, the main source of data were the responses of the senior high school students from the survey questionnaire. These senior high school students were currently enrolled in private and public schools in Davao del Norte. Likewise, no single information will be included from the researcher's personal perspective to avoid bias. More so, survey questionnaire was used. According to Preston (2019), a survey questionnaire is used gathering statistical information about the attributes, attitudes, or actions of a population by a structured set of questions.

Finally, supplementary readings from internet sources, published materials, refereed journals, articles, newspapers, books and the like were done. The data that were gathered from these secondary sources were used to support the data that were gathered from the respondents.

Procedure

In collecting the data, the following procedures were undertaken: The researcher sought approval from the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study and gather data. Then, the researcher asked permission through letter from the Schools Division Superintendents in Davao del Norte. Finally, a letter of the same content was given to the school principals. Copies of the approved letters will be appended. Moreover, face-to-face distribution of the questionnaires was done with strict observance of the existing health protocols and safety measures to lessen or eliminate the threats of COVID-19.

The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents after having been validated by experts and reliability tested. Then, a collection of completed questionnaires followed. Finally, the data were tallied and treated with appropriate statistical tools.

Factor such as data contamination was managed by the researcher by keeping each response as highly confidential. This was expressed in the cover letter of the questionnaires. The researchers believed that if the respondents were made to understand the confidentiality of their responses, then, they would be able to answer the questionnaires with all sincerity.

Moreover, other factors that might affect the results of the study, such as the number of hours that were utilized by the respondents in answering the questionnaires, the condition of the room/area to which the questionnaire was answered, and the physical condition of the respondents while answering were considered by expressing these as reminders in the cover letter of the questionnaires.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using various statistical tools.

Descriptive Analysis. This study used frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Frequency and percentage were used to analyze the socioeconomic profile of the respondents. These were used to answer objective 1. While, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of environmental condition in terms of external and internal factors and behavioral factors in terms of social learning, cognitive, affective, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control influencing their decision to enroll in agriculture course in college. These were used to answer objectives 2 and 3.

<i>Mean Range</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The factor is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The factor is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The factor is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The factor is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The factor is never evident.

Inferential Statistics. In this study, multiple regression analysis was used to identify the factors that significantly influence senior high school students' decisions to enroll in agriculture courses in college.

Results and Discussion

Socioeconomic Profile of Senior High School Students

This section discusses the socioeconomic profile of senior high school (SHS) students in terms of age, gender, family income, parents' educational background, type of school and strand taken.

Table 2 shows the profile of SHS in terms of age. As reflected on Table 2 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 135 or 8.21% are aged 15 years old and below, 352 or 21.40% are aged 16 years old, 405 or 24.62% are aged 17 years old, 635 or 38.60% are aged 18 years old and 118 or 7.17% are aged 19 years old and above. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the data that majority of the SHS students 18 years old and few of them are aged 19 years old and above.

Table 2. *Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
15 years old and below	135	8.21%
16	352	21.40%
17	405	24.62%
18	635	38.60%
19 years old and above	118	7.17%
Total	1645	100.00%

The result is in consonance with the study of Granada (2021), who divulged that the average age of SHS students in the Philippine is 18 years old. This happens because the entry age of learners in the Philippine Educational System is 5 years old for Kindergarten. And, in most cases, as long as the learner is not accelerated or failed, as the case may be, when they reached the age of 18, they are most likely in the SHS already. Additionally, the finding shows affirmation with the study of Hickok (2019), that SHS is the fourth key stage in the Philippine Educational System. Consequently, children usually enter kindergarten at the age of 5. Hence, as long as they do not stop going to school and they are not accelerated nor failed along their journey, then, most probably, upon reaching the age of 17 or 18, they are already in the fourth key stage, the SHS level.

Table 3. *Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	655	39.82%
Female	990	60.18%
Total	1645	100.00%

Table 3 shows the profile of SHS in terms of sex. As reflected on Table 3 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 655 or 39.82% are males and 990 or 60.18% are females. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the table that there were more female SHS students than males.

The result negates the study of Bacaling et al. (2021), who found out that most of the SHS are composed of male students. They added that 62% of the total number of SHS students in Davao del Norte are males and such data says that males composed the majority of the population officially enrolled in the different tracks, strand and specialization in the SHS curriculum.

However, the result affirms the study of David (2018) who explicated that females composed the majority of the SHS students. This happens because most of the male learners are left behind, causing them to be the majority contributors of out-of-school children (OOSC). In fact, the data revealed that two-thirds (65.0%) of OOSC in the Philippines in 2017 were males.

Table 4 shows the profile of SHS in terms of their family monthly income. As reflected on Table 4 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 140 or 8.51% families are earning below Php5,000.00 per month, 431 or 26.20% families are earning Php5,001.00 to Php10,000.00 per month, 661 or 40.18% families are earning Php10,001.00 to Php20,000.00 per month, 341 or 20.73% families are earning Php20,001.00 to Php50,000.00 per month and 72 or 4.38% families are earning above Php50,000.00 per month. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the table that majority of families of SHS students are earning Php10,001.00 to Php20,000.00 every month and few of their families are earning above Php50,000.00 every month.

Table 4. Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Family Monthly Income

Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below Php5,000.00	140	8.51%
Php5,001.00 to Php10,000.00	431	26.20%
Php10,001.00 to Php20,000.00	661	40.18%
Php20,001.00 to Php50,000.00	341	20.73%
Above Php50,000.00	72	4.38%
Total	1645	100.00%

The result is in disagreement with the study of Lv (2017) who disclosed that the average family income of SHS students is Php 45,930. Further, the data entails that, most of the members of their families are graduates of technical/vocational school, bachelor, master or above, who aside from their daily wages they also have other source of income.

In different vein, the result agrees the study of Adzido et al. (2016) who unveiled that majority of the SHS students' families are earning Php 20,000.00 to Php 30,000.00 monthly. They added that the aforesaid income range is earned through salaries, wages, rent, interest, profits, sick benefits, pensions, gifts, dividends, securities and royalties.

Table 5 shows the profile of SHS in terms of their parents' educational attainment. As reflected on Table 5 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 94 or 5.71% of their mothers and 110 or 6.69% of their fathers are elementary level, 135 or 8.21% of their mothers and 425 or 25.83% of their fathers are elementary graduate, 228 or 13.86% of their mothers and 310 or 18.84% of their fathers are high school level, 501 or 30.46% of their mothers and 205 or 12.46% of their fathers are high school graduate, 305 or 18.54% of their mothers and 255 or 15.51% of their fathers are college level, 207 or 12.58% of their mothers and 198 or 12.04% of their fathers are college graduate, 103 or 6.26% of their mothers and 82 or 4.98% of their fathers are masteral level, and 72 or 4.38% of their mothers and 60 or 3.65% of their fathers are masteral graduate. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the table that majority of mothers of the respondents are high school graduate while majority of their fathers are elementary graduate. Further, few of the parents of the respondents are masteral graduate.

The result is consistent with the study of Nelson (2019) who disclosed that most of the parents of SHS learners are high school graduates and few of them are able to finish their baccalaureate degrees. Also, he found out that these parents prefer to have their children in school to fulfill the family expectations or obligations.

Table 5. Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Parents' Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Level	94	5.71%	110	6.69%
Elementary Graduate	135	8.21%	425	25.83%
High School Level	228	13.86%	310	18.84%
High School Graduate	501	30.46%	205	12.46%
College Level	305	18.54%	255	15.51%
College Graduate	207	12.58%	198	12.04%
Masteral Level	103	6.26%	82	4.98%
Masteral Graduate	72	4.38%	60	3.65%
Total	1645	100.00%	1645	100.00%

On the other hand, the result negates the study of Chiu and Khoo (2015) who revealed that most of the parents of SHS students are college graduate. They added that these parents inculcate the long-term benefits of acquiring a college degree among their children.

Table 6 shows the profile of SHS in terms of type of school. As reflected on Table 6 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 985 or 59.88% studied in public schools, and 660 or 40.12% studied in private schools. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the table that majority of

respondents studied in public schools.

Table 6. Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Type of School

<i>Type Of School</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Public	985	59.88%
Private	660	40.12%
Total	1645	100.00%

The result is in harmony with the study of de la Fuente (2021) who unwrapped that even with the implementation of the voucher program of the government, enrollment of SHS students in private schools is less than the number of SHS students enrolled in public schools. In the 2019-2020 enrollment data of the Department of Education, only 42.51% of the SHS are enrolled in private schools while the rest 57.49% are in public schools.

Moreover, the finding is parallel to report of National Center for Education Statistics (2023) that of the overall 53.9 million K–12 students, 9% or almost 4.9 million were enrolled in private schools, and the remaining 91% or over 49 million were enrolled in public schools.

Table 7 shows the profile of SHS in terms of strand taken. As reflected on Table 7 that out of the 1645 SHS students, 201 or 12.22% are taking Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), 329 or 20.00% are taking General Academic Strand (GAS), 95 or 5.78% are taking Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), 56 or 3.40% are taking Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), 294 or 17.87% are taking Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Agriculture-Related and 670 or 40.73% are taking Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Non Agriculture-Related. Moreover, it could be gleaned on the table that majority of the respondents are taking Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Non Agriculture-Related while only few of them are taking Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM).

Table 7. Profile of SHS Students in Terms of Strand Taken

<i>Strand Taken</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
STEM	201	12.22%
GAS	329	20.00%
HUMSS	95	5.78%
ABM	56	3.40%
TVL-Agriculture	294	17.87%
TVL-Non Agriculture	670	40.73%
Total	1645	100.00%

The result is in disagreement with the study of Amarille (2019) who unconcealed that three most chosen strands among SHS students are GAS (General Academic Strand) followed by HUMSS (Humanities and Social Sciences), then CSS (Computer System Servicing). Their preferences are affected by personal factor, family, peer, and market demand.

Likewise, the result negates the study of Robles (2018) who expounded that the top three preferred strand in SHS are STEM, ABM, and GAS. This happens because, most of the students aspire to be in the field of medicine, engineering, business, and other-related careers. Also, their preferences are significantly affected by their skills, motivations, interests and personal characteristics.

Level of Environmental Condition of the Senior High School Students

This section discusses the level of environmental condition of the SHS students in terms of external factors (family income and parents' educational attainment) and internal factors (type of school as public or private, and strand taken).

Table 8 shows the level environmental condition of the SHS in terms of external factors. As reflected on Table 8 that the level of environmental condition of SHS in terms of family income is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 2.83. This means that family income as an external factor is sometimes evident. Hence, SHS students consider their family's income in enrolling agriculture course in college.

The result is in agreement with the study of Kinsler and Pavan (2021) who explicated that family income is a determinant of students' decision in enrolling a course in college. It significantly affects students choice of field of study in higher education. As such, students whose family income is lower than the minimum, but are academically performing, tend to find scholarship offerings to finance their studies.

On the other hand, it could also be gleaned on Table 8 that environmental condition of SHS in terms of parents' educational attainment is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 3.24. This means that parents' educational attainment as an external factor is sometimes evident. Thus, SHS students take into consideration the educational attainment of their parents in enrolling an agriculture course in college.

The result is parallel to the study conducted by Nelson (2019) who revealed that parents' educational attainment is a significant among adolescents' educational aspirations. Sanchez et al. (2016) added that parents' education is a determinant of students' choice of course

in tertiary education.

Table 8. *Level of Environmental Condition of the SHS Students in Terms External Factors*

<i>External Factors</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Family Income	0.55	2.83	Moderate
Parents' Educational Attainment	0.65	3.24	Moderate
Overall	0.60	3.04	Moderate

In general, as reflected on Table 8, the level environmental condition of the SHS in terms of external factors (family income and parents' educational attainment) is sometimes evident as indicated by the overall mean value of 3.04. On the one hand, the overall standard deviation is less than 1.00 which means that the responses are homogeneous and closely revolved around the mean value.

The result is in conformance with the study of Kauppi et al. (2022) who explicated that parent's occupation and socioeconomic status as defined by the income of their family as well as parents' educational attainment influence the decision of their children in enrolling a course in college. They expounded that these factors directly affect students decision in choosing what course to enroll in college.

Likewise, the finding agrees the study of Behnke et al. (2019) who found out that socioeconomic status, and educational level of parents affect their children's choice of what course to enroll in college. Likewise, they explained that Filipino children tend to follow the footsteps of their parents. As such, they try to emulate what their parents' have achieved in life.

Table 9 shows the level of environmental condition of the SHS in terms of internal factors. As reflected on Table 9 that the level of environmental condition of SHS in terms of type of school is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 2.93. This means that the type of school, whether public or private, as an internal factor is sometimes evident.

The result is in consonance with the study of Ouano (2019) who expounded that choosing a career as determined by the course one chooses to enroll in college is greatly affected by the type of school where one finishes his/her basic education. Additionally, most of the opt to enroll in state colleges because agriculture-related courses are commonly offered.

On the other hand, it could also be gleaned on Table 9 that environmental condition of SHS in terms of the strand taken is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 3.30. This means that the strand taken as an internal factor is sometimes evident.

The result disagrees the study conducted by Quintos and Caballes (2022) who divulged that there is a mismatch between the enrolled strand of the students in SHS and their enrolled courses in college. Among the topmost reasons why SHS students did not take the college course align with their strand are family, friends and peer pressures, and accessibility of the program in the nearby university or college.

Table 9. *Level of Environmental Condition of the SHS Students in Terms Internal Factors*

<i>Internal Factors</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Type of School	0.62	2.93	Moderate
Strand Taken	0.71	3.30	Moderate
Overall	0.67	3.12	Moderate

In general, as reflected on Table 9, the level environmental condition of the SHS in terms of internal factors (type of school as public or private and strand taken) is sometimes evident as indicated by the overall mean value of 3.12. On the one hand, the overall standard deviation is less than 1.00 which means that the responses are homogeneous and closely revolved around the mean value.

The result is in conformity with the study of Uyar (2021) who unconcealed that both type of school and strand taken affect students' choice in choosing what course to enroll in college. These factors determine the quality of instruction they received which would be of great advantage in their success in their college journey.

Likewise the finding concurs the study of Garg et al. (2022) who unveiled that the type of school and strand taken greatly affects ones strengths, passions, and skills. They added that the school as a learning institution play a crucial role in expanding students' knowledge and skills and the strand is designed and specialized to match the students' interests in preparation for college.

The Level of Behavioral Factors of Senior High School Students

This section discusses the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of social learning, cognitive, affective, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control.

As reflected in Table 10 that the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of social learning is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 3.29. This means that social learning as a behavioral factor is sometimes evident. Consequently, the SHS students' decision in choosing an agriculture course in college is affected by their teachers who are passionate about agriculture and effectively communicate its importance.

The result confirms the study of Fimalino et al. (2020) who found out that students decision in enrolling a course in college is a result

of how teachers helped them in discovering their strengths and weaknesses. As such, teachers who are able to provide students an experience that enable them to unleash their potentials and appreciate the importance of agriculture-related subjects could evidently encourage students to enroll in agriculture course in college.

Moreover, it could be gleaned on the Table 10 that the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of cognitive is high as indicated by the mean value of 3.42. This means that cognitive as a behavioral factor is oftentimes evident. Accordingly, SHS students consider their knowledge and skills as well as their intellectual capacity in enrolling agriculture course in college.

The result is in harmony with the study of Okiror and Otabong (2015) who stressed that the students' grade point averages (GPA), as a measure of their performance in school, mostly through their cognitive abilities, affect their decision in enrolling a course in college. When a student perform well in agriculture-related subjects then most probably, he/she will choose to enroll agriculture course in college.

On the one hand, as reflected in Table 10 that the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of affective is high as indicated by the mean value of 3.75. This means that affective as a behavioral factor is oftentimes evident. Consequently, SHS students believe that their personality, qualities and character are appropriate for agriculture course.

The result is in agreement with the study of Sabir et al. (2018) who disclosed that their interest in subject determine their choice of what course to enroll in college. In such case, when students see that they could handle the challenges and difficulties of the agriculture course that they are planning to enroll they, would probably decide to enroll.

Further, as shown in Table 10 that the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of subjective norm is moderate as indicated by the mean value of 3.26. This means that subjective as a behavioral factor is sometimes evident. Accordingly, SHS students decision to enroll in agriculture course in college is a manifestation of their parents' personal choice, expecting that they would be in alleviating the family's situation.

The result is parallel to the study of Su et al. (2016) who undraped that the preference of their parents affect their choice in enrolling a course in college. In connection to this, when parents are successful in their chosen career in agriculture, then most probably, they will encourage and motivate their children to take similar courses in college.

Furthermore, as shown in Table 10 that the level of behavioral factors of SHS students in terms of perceived behavioral control is high as indicated by the mean value of 3.65. This means that perceived behavioral control as a behavioral factor is oftentimes evident. Consequently, SHS students find it helpful and advantageous in their part if they opt to enroll in agriculture course.

The result shows parallelism to the study conducted by Sidin et al. (2018) who explicated that when students behavioral perception on the course affect their choice of career in the future. As such, when they perceived that agriculture is easy, interesting and relaxing, then, they would likely enroll in agriculture course in college.

Table 10. *Level of Behavioral Factors of the SHS Students*

<i>Behavioral Factors</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Social Learning	0.64	3.29	Moderate
Cognitive	0.75	3.42	High
Affective	0.50	3.75	High
Subjective Norm	0.65	3.26	Moderate
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.67	3.65	High
Overall	0.64	3.47	High

In general, as reflected on Table 10, the level of behavioral factors of the SHS in terms of social learning, cognitive, affective, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control is oftentimes evident as indicated by the overall mean value of 3.47. On the one hand, the overall standard deviation is less than 1.00 which means that the responses are homogeneous and closely revolved around the mean value.

The result is in consonance with the study of Agarwla (2018) who opined that students' decision to enroll in agriculture course in college is a manifestation of their several factors that may have a direct or indirect effects on their choice of career in the future. These factors include, parents', friends and peers influence and training in school which could enhance their skills, competencies, and abilities among others.

Consequently, the finding shows affirmation with the study conducted by Soria and Stebleton (2018) who accentuated that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors affect students choice of the course to enroll in college. Satisfying their parents' desire, financial capacities as well as their cognitive levels and how they see agriculture as a career or job in the future contribute to their decision in enrolling an agriculture course in college.

Significance on the Factors Influencing the Decision of Senior High School Students to Enroll in Agricultural Courses

This section discusses the factors that significantly influence the decision of senior high school students to enroll in agricultural courses. The extents of influence of the six factors were shown through the standardized beta values and their significance was determined through the p values as reflected in Table 11.

Table 11. *Significance on the Factors Influencing the Decision of SHS Students to Enroll in Agriculture Courses*

Factors	Decision of SHS Students to Enroll in Agriculture Courses			
	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value	Interpretation
Environmental	.036	.373	.010	Significant
Social Learning	-.007	-.066	.948	Not Significant
Cognitive	.064	.654	.014	Significant
Affective	-.136	-1.373	.173	Not Significant
Subjective Norm	.249	2.518	.013	Significant
Perceived Behavioral Control	.102	.935	.352	Not Significant
	R = .318			
	R ² = .101			
	F = 193.043			
	p-value = .000			

Specifically, the standard coefficient beta of environmental factor is 0.036 and it is positive. The positive beta value means positive effect, and it is significant, as reflected by the p-value of 0.010. Thus, it could be stated that environment (internal and external) as a factor has significant influence on the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses. Further, It could be stated that environmental (internal and external) factor has significant positive influence to the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses. Thus, a change in the level of environmental (internal and external) factor could mean a change in the decision level of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses or when the environmental (internal and external) factor goes up or down, as the case may be, the decision level of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses. shall also go up or down.

The finding is in affirmation with the study of Kazi and Akhlaq (2017) who accented that the internal and external environment influence their career choice. Likewise, their decision to enroll in agriculture course in college is determined by how these environmental factors help in shaping their choices in life.

Moreover, the standard coefficient beta of social learning has the lowest beta value of -0.007 and it is negative. This implies that social learning as a factor negatively influence the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses. However, as reflected by p-value of .948, the regression model is not significant. Thus, it could be stated that social learning as a factor has no significant influence on SHS students decision to enroll in agriculture courses. Hence, a change in the level of social learning factor could not mean a change in SHS students decision to enroll in agriculture courses, or as the level of social learning factor goes up or down as the case may be, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses shall remain in the same level.

The finding negates the study of Olaosebikan and Olusakin (2019) who stressed that social learning factors shaped students' decision in enrolling a course in college. In the same manner, these factors could either strengthened or weakened students' choice in enrolling an agriculture course.

On the one hand, the standard coefficient beta of cognitive factor is 0.064 and it is positive. This implies that cognitive as a factor influences the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture courses. As reflected by the p-value of 0.014, the regression model is significant. Thus, it could be stated that cognitive factor has significant influence on the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course. Further, It could be stated that cognitive factor has positive significant influence to decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course. Thence, a change in the level of cognitive factor could mean a change also in the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course or when the level of cognitive factor goes up or down, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course shall also go up or down, as the case may be.

The result is shows affirmation with the study of Edwards and Quinter (2021) who found out that the cognitive capabilities of students influence their choice of what course to enroll in college. They added that, majority of the SHS students who responded in their study, agreed that their knowledge, skills, abilities and intellectual capacities positively affect their decision to enroll in agriculture course in college. This is so because they find these courses as challenging which require analysis and deep understanding.

Furthermore, the standard coefficient beta of affective factor is -0.136. This implies that affective factor negatively influences the decision of SHS students to enroll in Agriculture course. However, as reflected on the table that the p-value is 0.173, the regression model is not significant. Therefore, it could be stated that affective as a factor has no significant influence on SHS students decision to enroll in agriculture courses. Hence, a change in the level of affective factor could not mean a change in the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course, or as the level of affective factor goes up or down as the case may be, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course shall remain in the same level.

The finding disagrees the result of Malgwi et al. (2015) who disclosed that interest in the agriculture-related subjects, as an affective factor, influence students decision to enroll agriculture course in college. Also, when students are able to see that their personality fits the requirement of the course, then, they will opt to enroll and choose agriculture as a career in the future.

Adding on, the standard coefficient beta of subjective as a moderating factor is 0.249 and it is positive. This implies that subjective

factor positively influence the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course and it is significant as reflected by the p-value of 0.013. Further, a change in the level of subjective factor could mean a change also in the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course or when the level of subjective factor goes up or down, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course shall also go up or down, as the case may be. Hence, subjective factor could have a positive moderating influence to the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture.

The result is consonance with the study of Jalcobia et al. (2018) who revealed that the choices of their parents and peers, as well as their personal preferences influence the their decision on what college course they will take. In this case, when a students opted to enroll in agriculture course in college, it is a manifestation of their parents, peers and personal preferences.

Finally, standard coefficient beta of perceived behavioral control as a moderating factor is 0.102 and it is positive. This implies that perceived behavioral control factor positively influence the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course. However, it is not significant as reflected by the p-value of 0.352. Further, a change in the level of perceived behavioral control factor could not mean a change also in the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course or when the level of perceived behavioral control factor goes up or down, as the case may be, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course remains unchanged. Hence, perceived behavioral control factor do not have a moderating influence to the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture.

The finding contradicts the study of Conley et al. (2016) who explained that the students behavior towards the subject influence their choice of what course to enroll in college. Banking on this statement, when students are able to develop a positive behavior towards the subject, then they would be able to decide on the what course they will take in college. In same way, they will enroll in agriculture course in college when they perceive that this course will give them greater advantage in the future.

Scrutinizing further the data in Table 11, it is found out that not all standardized coefficient beta were positive. The analysis illustrates that only two factors of the independent variable, namely, environmental and cognitive factors have positive Beta values and significant as reflected by the p-values of 0.010 and 0.014 respectively. While the other two factors, namely, social learning and affective factors have negative Beta values and not significant as reflected by the p-values of 0.948 and 0.173 respectively. This further explains that environmental and cognitive factors positively contribute to the variations in the level of the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course and all are significant. Hence, increases in the levels of these factors could mean an increase in the level of the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course or when these factors go up or down, the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course shall also go up or down, as the case may be. Further, an increase or decrease in the levels of social learning and affective factors could not mean an increase or decrease in the level of decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course does not necessarily go up or down.

Additionally, only one of the two factors of the moderating variable is significant. Subjective as a moderating factor significantly influence the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course, while, perceived behavioral control as a moderating factor does not significantly influence the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course. Hence, subjective factors have a moderating influence on the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course while perceived behavioral control does not have a moderating influence on the decision of SHS students to enroll in agriculture course.

Finally, in the results manifest that only 10.10% of the variance in the regression analysis are explained by the six predictor factors as indicated by the $R^2 = 0.101$. Also, this signifies that 89.9% of the variation of the display of performance is attributed to other factors.

The results support the Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) which emphasizes that parents within the family, characters on children's TV, friends within their peer group, and teachers at school are influential models in which a child is more likely to attend to and imitate. The results imply that SHS students' decision to enroll in an agriculture course in college is greatly affected by these influential models around him/her. More so, their career choice in the future is greatly influenced by the people around them perceive agriculture as a course.

The finding is parallel to Brown's Values-Based Career Theory (2002) which stressed that values as cognitive structures are the basis for self-evaluation and one's evaluation of others. In relation to this, how family members and peers perceive and evaluate agriculture courses greatly affect or influence one's decision in enrolling a course in college. In the same manner, SHS students' decision in enrolling an agriculture course in college is greatly affected by how family members and peers helped them perceive the aforesaid.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, majority of the SHS students 18 years old and few of them were aged 19 years old and above, there were more female SHS students than males, majority of families of SHS students earned Php10,001.00 to Php20,000.00 every month and few of their families earned above Php50,000.00 every month, majority of mothers of the respondents were high school graduate while majority of their fathers are elementary graduate, and few of their parents were masteral graduate, most of respondents studied in public schools, and most of them took Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Non Agriculture-Related while only few of them took Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM).

Second, the environmental conditions of SHS in terms of family income and parents' educational attainment were sometimes evident. Apparently, external factors such as social support, opportunities, and resources are evidently available to SHS students. In terms of type of school and strand taken, these internal factors were sometimes evident. Seemingly, internal factors such as school training as well as the knowledge, skills, and competencies learned by the SHS students were recognizable. In terms of social learning, this factor was sometimes evident. Consequently, teachers were passionate about agriculture and could effectively communicate its importance to SHS students. In terms of cognitive, this factor was oftentimes evident. Ostensibly, SHS students oftentimes show their knowledge and skills as well as their intellectual capacity in enrolling agriculture course in college. In terms of affective, this factor was oftentimes evident. Hence, SHS students oftentimes believed that their personality, qualities and character are appropriate for agriculture course. In terms of subjective norm, this factor was sometimes evident. Accordingly, SHS students sometimes manifest their parents' personal choice, expecting that they would help in alleviating the family's situation in choosing agriculture course in college. And, in terms of perceived behavioral control, this factor was oftentimes evident. Therefore, SHS students oftentimes find it helpful and advantageous in their part if they opt to enroll in agriculture course.

As to the outcomes of the multiple regression analysis, there existed a positive significant influence of environmental, cognitive and subjective norms factors towards SHS decision to enroll on agriculture course in college. Hence, any increase or decrease in the levels of environmental and cognitive factors shall also mean an increase or decrease in the level of SHS decision to enroll on agriculture course in college, as the case may be. However, no significant influence existed on social learning, affective and perceived behavioral control factors towards SHS choice to enroll on agriculture course in college. Thus, the level of SHS decision to enroll on agriculture course in college remain unchanged even if social learning, affective and perceived behavioral control factors changed.

In the light of the findings and conclusions drawn, the researcher offers the following recommendations:

The Colleges of Agriculture may use the results of this study as basis in improving their recruitment strategies to increase their enrollment in agriculture courses. They may revisit their curricula and policies so that it would be responsive to the environmental conditions, cognitive levels and subjective norms orientation of the students who wish too enroll in agriculture courses.

The educators and policymakers may utilize the findings of this study by re-calibrating their approaches and strategies in the delivery of quality agricultural education whenever needed. And, by doing their roles and responsibilities inspired by the pressing needs of those who wish to enroll agriculture course, they may able to significantly contribute in achieving a more sustainable and resilient agricultural sector of the country.

The Senior High School students may gain great advantage on the results of this study by embarking on the idea that their choices of today could significantly affect their future career in life. And by taking serious and responsible actions on their decisions in enrolling agriculture course in college they may be able to realize that they could actually contribute in the economy of the country, and of the progress of the nation, in general.

The results of this study may be gainful for parents by using the empirical data as their motivating factors in doing their roles and responsibilities in the education of their children. And, by considering that their decisions affect the choices of their children, the much needed guidance and counselling may be offered by them.

Finally, future researchers may utilize the results of this study as a springboard for future studies particularly in topics related to students' decision making in choosing agriculture as a career. They may also use the literature and findings of this study to enrich similar topics using other methods and theories. Moreover, they may conduct similar studies in different locale and looking into the limitations of this study to further validate its results.

References

- Ahmed, K., Sharif, N. & Ahmad, N. (2017). Factors Influencing Student's Career Choice: Empirical Evidence From Business Students. *Journal of Southeast Asia Research*, 1-15. DOI:10.5171/2017.718849
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179–211.
- Alphones, M. (2016). Parental factors influencing career choice among high school students in Nairobi county. University of Nairobi.
- Babbie, E. (2015). *Survey research methods*. 2nd ed., Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Baker, L. (2023). Recruiting Strategically: Increasing Enrollment in Academic Programs of Agriculture. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 54(3), 54-66.
- Bhandari, P. (2021). Correlational Research | When & How to Use. <https://tinyurl.com/4zs3aza4>
- Bozgeyikli, H. (2020). The relationship between high school students' psychological needs and human value perceptions. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.12.403>
- Bowen, B. (2016). Factors influencing career choices of urban agricultural education students. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 46(2), 24–35. doi:10.5032/jae.02024

- Bushman, B., & Huesmann, L. (2021). Effects of televised violence on aggression. In D. Singer & J. Singer (Eds.), *Handbook of children and the media* (pp. 223–254). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cano, J. & Bankston, J. (2022). Factors which influence participation and nonparticipation of ethnic minority youth in Ohio 4-H programs. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 33(1), 23-29
- Cross, T., Slater, Rb. (2017). The commanding wealth advantage of college-bound white students. *The Journal of Blacks in Higher Education* 15(1): 80–90
- Ferry, NM. (2016). Factors influencing career choices of adolescents and young adults in rural Pennsylvania. *Journal of Extension* 44(3).
- Hayes, A. (2022). *Introduction to Mediation, Moderation, and Conditional Process Analysis Third Edition*.
- Hoskey, M. (2018). Opinions of public school administrators concerning agricultural education. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Missouri, Columbia.
- Johnson, M., & Mortimer, J. (2022). Career choice and development from a social perspective. In *Career Choice and Development IV*. Brown & Associates eds. Jossey-Bass A Wiley Company, San Francisco.
- Kaneez, B. & Medha. K. (2018). Factors Influencing Grade 10 Students' Career Choice in Mauritius May 2018. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development* 7(2). DOI:10.6007/IJARPED/v7-i2/4081
- Kendra, C. (2022). What Is a Correlational Study? <https://tinyurl.com/53nvrwya>
- Kim, M. (2021). The relationship between thinking style differences and career choices for high-achieving students. *Roeper Review* 33(4): 252–262.
- Kowalczyk, D. (2018). *Descriptive Statistics, Title and List, 2003-2018*. <http://Study.com>
- Krueger, D., & Riesenber, L. (2021). Careers in agriculture as perceived by high school juniors and seniors. *Proceedings of the Eighteenth Annual National Agricultural Education Research Meeting*, 63-69.
- Lam, J. (2022). Determinants of educational plans of the in determinant high school graduates. *The Journal of Educational Administration*, 20(2), 213-229
- Lent, R. (2018). Toward a unifying social cognitive theory of career and academic interest, choice, and performance. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 45(1): 79–122.
- Lent, R. W., Brown, S. D. & Hackett, G. (1994). Toward a Unifying Social Cognitive Theory of Career and Academic Interest, Choice and Performance. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Volume 45, pp. 79 – 112.
- Mallory, M. & Sommer, R. (2016). Student images of agriculture: Survey highlights and recommendations. *Journal of The American Association of Teachers Education in Agriculture*, 27(4), 15-17
- Manyasi, A. (2021). *Global Influential Factors for Choice of Agriculture Related Courses among Students: A Review Paper*.
- Marshall, T., Herring, D., & Briers, G. (2022). Factors associated with enrollment in agricultural science and membership in the FFA in Texas. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 33(4)
- Mccombes, S. (2019). *Descriptive Research*. <https://tinyurl.com/2p855226>
- Messerli, F. (2022). Chocolate consumption, cognitive function, and Nobel laureates. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 367, 1562-1564.
- Nazareno Al., Lopez Mjf., Gestiada Ga., Martinez Mp., Roxas-Villanueva, RM. (2021). An artificial neural network approach in predicting career strand of incoming senior high school students. In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1245(1): 012005. IOP Publishing
- Neda (2018). NEDA-CAR joins advocacy for more enrollment in agriculture courses
- Nunnaly, J. (2013). Where do the descriptors for Cronbach's alpha values come from? <https://www.researchgate.net./cronbach>
- Picciano, A. (2015). *Educational Research Primer*. London: Continuum Press.
- Pimpa, N. (2023). The influence of family, peers, and education agents on Thai students' choices of international education. In: *The Australia International Education Conference*, p. 1–21.
- Preston, V. (2019). *Questionnaire Survey*. <https://tinyurl.com/52mwxdhk>
- Price, C. (2019). An examination of factors influencing students not to enroll in secondary vocational education. *Summary of Research*,

Department of Agricultural Education, Columbus:The Ohio State University.

Rea, L. & Parker, R. (2018). *Designing and conducting survey research*. 2nd ed., San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.

Reyes, R. (2019). *Factors Affecting Senior High School Students' Choice to Veer Away from Agricultural Courses in San Juan, Batangas*

Rossetti, R., Elliot, J., Price, C., & Mcclay, P. (2020). *An examination of factors influencing students not to enroll in secondary vocational education. Summary of Research, Department of Agricultural Education, Columbus: The Ohio State University.*

Rababah, A. (2016). *Factors Influencing the Students' Choice of Accounting as a Major: The case of X University in United Arab Emirates. International Business Research, 9(10), 25-32. DOI:10.5539/ibr.v9n10p25*

Sansom, R. (2022). *Theory of Planned Behavior*. <https://tinyurl.com/mw8py6j3>

Schein, E. (2018). *Career dynamics: matching individual and organizational needs*. Boston, MA: Addison Wesley Publishing Company

SEARCA.ORG. *Enrollment in agri-courses continues to decline*. <https://tinyurl.com/ykxvf99w>

Spokane, A. (2019). *A review of research on person environment congruence in Holland's theory of careers. Journal of Vocational Behavior 26(3): 306-343.*

Sutphin, D., Mora, D., & Newsom-Stewart, L. (2019). *Student's Rationale For Selection Of Agriculturally Related Courses In High School By Gender And Ethnicity. Journal of Agricultural Education 36(2). DOI:10.5032/jae.1995.02054*

Trefry, S. (2017). *What is sample size?* <https://tinyurl.com/2p8zmnha>

Udoh, N., & Sanni, Kb. (2017). *Parental background variables and the career choice of secondary school students in Uyo local government area, Nigeria. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences 3(1).*

Uyar, A., Gungormus, A., & Kuzey, C. (2021). *Factors Affecting Students Career Choice in Accounting: The case of a Turkish University. American Journal of Business Education, 4(10), 29-38. DOI:10.19030/ajbe.v4i10.6061*

Wang, M. & Degol, J. (2018). *Motivational pathways to STEM career choices: using expectancy – value perspective to understand individual and gender differences in STEM fields. Developmental Review 33(1): 304-340.*

Wildman, M. & Torres, R. (2022). *Factors Identified When Selecting A Major In Agriculture June 2001. Journal of Agricultural Education 42(2). DOI:10.5032/jae.2001.02046*

Yazici, S. & Yazici A. (2020). *Students' Choice of College Major and their perceived fairness of the procedure Evidence from Turkey. Educational Research and Evaluation, 16(4), 371-382. DOI:10.1080/13893611.2010.528196.*

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jonathan M. Almanzor, MExEd

Kapalong National High School

Department of Education – Philippines

Chenie Kate Almanzor, LPT

Benigno Q. Martir National High School

Department of Education – Philippines